

The World's First Interactive 5G Music Concert: Professional Quality Networked Music Over a Commodity Network Infrastructure

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ABSTRACT

The principle of distributed music with musicians performing in different locations and connected via the Internet has been investigated over several decades, with numerous performances demonstrated as a proof of concept. The scope of these performances, however, was either experimental or amateur; furthermore, most of them used a dedicated network infrastructure with correspondingly high costs. In contrast, this paper describes the first commodity hardware-based 5G distributed music event at professional quality with jazz music celebrity Jamie Cullum and a band of six musicians distributed over three venues, each separated by distances of over 100 miles. This paper describes the general motivation of the event, the technical setup in terms of audio, video and 5G networking and the technical as well as artistic challenges overcome.

low-latency audio, sound engineering, digital signal processing, distributed systems, 5G

1. INTRODUCTION

With respect to music, the Internet has so far mainly been used for the interchange of audio files or separate audio tracks within the music production process. Satisfying musical interactions between musicians located in different locations, however, represents a more complex field of application: Cognitive, technical and purely musical aspects pose serious challenges on a networked music performance in order to emulate the experience of interactive, spontaneous performance in the same room. Until approximately 2005 the idea of a network music performance over the internet was generally considered impractical as the total one-way delay between two performers is supposed to remain below 25 ms [1] which appeared to be problematic if not unrealistic especially with respect to home-consumer networks such as ADSL [2]. Figure 1 shows the total path a

signal has to pass in order to be transmitted via the Internet. Each stage is marked in either white, light grey or dark grey color. White indicates no additional delay, light and dark grey indicate slight and significant delays respectively. On top of the natural path, the electronic path and the digital path, the Internet adds often significant delays due to detours introduced by the routing of packages and due to jitter buffers in order to compensate delay variations. Due to this, (co-author) Alexander Carôt developed the Soundjack software and released it in 2006. Soundjack suits this transmission structure and allows to verify a system's sound card settings and the actual network parameters in terms of an individual parameter optimization in order to support any kind of underlying networking infrastructure. In terms of audio, his work was mainly inspired by the SoundWIRE project and its successor Jacktrip lead by Chris Chafe at Stanford based CCRMA [3]. Regarding video, the main inspiration was a low-latency video processing system developed by Jeremy Cooperstock at McGill University [4]. Soundjack has evolved into a leading product in networked music performances, and is freely available under [5]. Especially in the current COVID-19 crisis the system experiences 1,500 page views and hosts more than 50 interactive sessions in average per day using various network infrastructures. Besides Soundjack several other projects have evolved which follow either similar or alternative approaches of compromised musical interaction. An excellent overview of available systems of the year 2016 can be found in [6]. Apart from the applied technology the set of possible interaction approaches is outlined in chapter five of [1]. Rather than discussing the concept of distributed music in general this paper addresses the non-compromised realistic interaction approach with professional musicians in form of a public concert using a 5G commodity network infrastructure. Given these three fundamental frame conditions and their inherent complexity this special use case represents a novelty in the domain of distributed music.

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2. PROBLEM AND GOAL

The domain of distributed music has evolved significantly over the last 10 years; yet, it still is considered a niche ap-

Figure 1. Total signal path of an audio signal.

plication rarely taken seriously within the engineering and music community. Although numerous official and private performances in various network settings turned out to be successful, distributed music is typically not used as a replacement for the conventional use case with musicians performing in the same rehearsing space on the same stage. Most demonstrations and concerts to date have been experimental in nature, including a group of enthusiastic but mainly amateur or semiprofessional volunteers. Furthermore, these events typically used a dedicated network infrastructure with speeds of several Gbps including quality-of-service policies (QoS) [2] which provided excellent quality but excluded a wider potential group of participants due to the associated high costs and limited availability. On the one hand the LOLA project [7] represents a professional solution which takes advantage of such high-capacity network infrastructures, however, in turn it cannot support home-consumer Internet endpoints. On the other hand Soundjack has been supporting narrow-bandwidth Internet endpoints such as DSL or cable modems since 2006, however, for technical reasons users must still use a cabled LAN connection to the router which implies a lack of local flexibility and in turn artistic freedom. For these reasons, we have developed and proven a concept for a public professional quality network music concert that uses a 5G network, enabling access to the general music-making public as 5G networks are being rolled out over the coming months and years.

3. CONCEPT

With respect to our goal of a professional distributed music event, we first had to identify a frame including a clear intention and motivation. After several controversial discussions we eventually decided to demonstrate how technology – and especially with the advent of 5G [8] – can remove barriers to learning: The delivery of low-latency connectivity everywhere will enable an Internet of Skills [9] where skills can be shared with others wherever they may live, work and play. In that context, we wanted to bring together music teachers and aspiring musicians. We partnered with the music charity “Music for All” to find a music teacher who was well known in public, could straddle musical genres, could involve and communicate with musicians and an audience compellingly, and who was a consummate instrumentalist and singer, but with a non-traditional route into music. With all of that at stake, only a limited number of professional musicians could be approached: to our delight the famous popular jazz musician Jamie Cullum approached the opportunity with enthusiasm.

4. REALIZATION

For the official network music session we wanted Jamie Cullum (on vocals and piano) to be performing and teaching in London, while connected to a remote location in Birmingham (three amateur musicians on drums, bass and guitar) and a remote location in Bristol (three amateur musicians on vocals, saxophone and keyboards) via a 5G network. The remote amateur musicians were selected by Jamie Cullum himself via an open casting call for applications [10]. With the target of achieving expected audio end-to-end latencies of below 25 ms following the findings of [1], we selected the Soundjack software. The video capture component of Soundjack was not used because it currently supports a 4:3 resolution only. Mapping this format to our sponsored video panels of 16:9 screen resolution would not have allowed us to use the full space of the screen. Therefore, we used the UltraGrid software [11] as a substitute, which supports the 16:9 format. Figure 2 illustrates the complete hardware and network setup for each of the involved sites. The following subsections refer to this figure and describe the technical setup in further detail.

4.1 London

The London site consists of the King’s College London (KCL) Strand Campus where core network equipment was located and the 2,000 year-old Roman Amphitheatre beneath Guildhall in the City of London where the performance took place. The two locations are interconnected via a dedicated Virtual Private Circuit provided by British Telecommunications (BT) with a capacity of 1 Gbps and an RTT of 1 ms. On the Guildhall side, the setup consists of a base-band-unit (BBU) 5G Antenna and a Customer Premises Equipment (CPE), which is equivalent to a 5G user device. The CPE connects over 1 Gbps Ethernet to the desktop computer that handles the audio and video streaming. Soundjack and Ultragrid clients run on the desktop

computer and transmit/receive audio and video feeds.

The audio interface Focusrite Scarlett 2i4 [12] was patched to the audio mixer where the sound engineers balanced the two inputs for vocals and piano as well as the incoming audio from the other sites to the PA. The computer was directly connected to a video matrix for displaying the videos from the remote sites to a series of on-stage video panels at full HD resolution at 30 Hz refresh rate. Each video panel displayed one of the remote musicians at life size. Similarly, the USB video camera was capturing live feed from the stage and transmitting it over the network to the remote sites via Ultragrid running on the desktop computer. The aggregated audio and video streams were sent to the CPE and from there transmitted over the 5G radio to the KCL core site on the Strand campus.

On the Strand campus, the virtualized 5G core processed the radio interface coming from the Guildhall and routed IP packets to the core infrastructure. The audio packets were directly transmitted to each site via a dedicated 10 Gbps link to Bristol and a VPN over public Internet to Birmingham in peer to peer mode. The video packets from each site were sent to the Virtual Network Function cloud where Ultragrid reflectors processed the camera feed from each site and multicast it to remote sites, thus offloading the encoding and multicasting overheads from the client devices. This leads to decongestion of the 1 Gbps uplinks on each desktop computer by reducing the video traffic to a single uplink stream instead of two uplink streams per site as would occur if the video was transmitted in peer to peer mode. By reducing the load on the low capacity user device network links and offloading part of the video processing to the cloud, each desktop client is able to perform audio encoding tasks more consistently. In combination with the above mentioned upload decongestion we expected higher network stability and lower latencies for the audio and video streams.

4.2 Bristol

In comparison to Figure 2, Figure 3 gives a more detailed visual impression of the hardware and network setup in Bristol: A desktop computer was used to run the Soundjack application for mixing and controlling the sound transmitted on the network. A high definition video camera was used to capture the live feed transmitted across the three sites using the Ultragrid software. Similarly, the feed from other sites was received on the Ultragrid software displayed on site. A Focusrite Scarlett 2i2 [12] was used as the sound card to connect the mixing console and in turn the musical instruments (piano, saxophone) and vocalist’s microphone to the Soundjack application.

Bristol’s Smart Internet Lab and ‘We the Curious’ museum were connected using the INITIATE test network comprised of a 10 Gbps Layer-2 Network connectivity between University of Bristol and King’s College London via the 5GUK Exchange [13] interconnection at Virtus’ data-center in Slough. Since we had to connect to the third site outside of the INITIATE test network, KCL was used as a gateway for the devices and Soundjack to communicate with each other. As shown in the figure, a L2 SDN switch

Figure 2. Illustration of the hardware and network setup in each of the involved sites.

Figure 3. Illustration of the hardware and network setup in each of the involved sites

is used at the Bristol network endpoint with access to the 5GUK Exchange over the JANET link. The Opendaylight SDN controller was used at the 5GUK Exchange as well as at the Bristol site to create the required flow rules to connect Bristol with the gateway at KCL.

4.3 Birmingham

The Royal Birmingham Conservatoire has a purpose built dedicated digital audio video infrastructure, which interconnects all of the venues and studios to any other space at low latency.

The East Side Jazz club was used for the performance with a set up consisting of three MacPro Desktop Computers. The first MacPro (MP1) acted as a dedicated audio transmission/receiver machine. MP1 running Soundjack received the audio from the SSL L300 mixing console via Dante Audio Network; the Dante Virtual Soundcard acted as the audio capture device within Soundjack which enabled audio to be routed directly to/from Soundjack to the console, PA, sub mixes for individual foldback for performers consisting of local and remote audio feeds and talk back channels for local and remote technicians. A full drum microphone set up was used along with guitar and bass microphones to capture the audio, which was mixed down to two channels for transmission to the remote sites. The second MacPro (MP2) acted as a dedicated video capture/transmission/receiver machine. MP2 running Ultragrid for video streaming received video captured using a BlackMagic Ultra Studio 4k Extreme from a HDSDI Video Camera. This enabled the video settings to be consistent from camera through to Ultragrid transmission. MP2 received video via Ultragrid from the remote locations, which was projected side by side via a Crestron video matrix. The third MacPro (MP3) mirrored in dual boot setup the install of both MP1 and MP2 as a redundant backup.

Birmingham City University’s dedicated research network and gateway was used for network connectivity to the Joint Academic Network (JANET), which provides high performance connection to the King’s VPN gateway. We use OpenVPN [14] to establish a UDP tunnel between Birmingham and King’s as a means of simplifying the routing configuration and avoiding port forwarding on academic firewalls. The OpenVPN client was running directly on the desktop computer at the Royal Conservatoire and thus required no additional network configuration on the physical infrastructure. Camera and audio streams were sent and received over the tunnel IP created by OpenVPN and the routing between sites was handled at the King’s College Strand campus infrastructure.

5. EVALUATION

Figure 4 gives a visual impression of the successful performance, in which Jamie Cullum performed two songs together with the remote musicians, providing feedback and suggestions on their playing. The audience consisted of about 100 invited people in London and around 50 additionally in Bristol and Birmingham.

Figure 4. Visual impression of the 5G music lesson with jazz celebrity Jamie Cullum in London and amateur musicians in Birmingham (left screen) and Bristol (right screen).

Especially for this event, we implemented a text logging feature that gave clear evidence in terms of latency, audio dropouts and reordered packets for each of the involved sites. Visualization of the log files leads to the graphs shown in Figures 5 and 8.

Figure 5 shows the data received from the Birmingham site. For the first 110 minutes the one-way latency (OWD) ranged between 12 ms and a maximum of 20 ms depending on the buffer states with respect to jitter, loss and sound card related clock drift. Right before the beginning of the official performance we increased the network buffer slightly, which resulted in a one-way latency between 18 and 26 ms. Altogether we measured 1,154 audio dropouts for the total amount of 200 minutes. This corresponded to a single dropout in a period of several seconds at almost regular intervals as explained below. These occasional signal errors could be concealed by our implemented error concealment and were inaudible to the audience. Furthermore, the applied increase of the buffer size also correlated with a decrease of audio dropouts: Buffer underruns were reduced to zero and buffer overruns to approximately 50 % resulting in even a larger dropout interval: In Figure 6, we present a five-minute (300 seconds) closeup of the London dropout graph starting at minute 200 of the total measurement duration.

The graph shows buffer overruns in intervals of approximately 25 seconds, which confirms and visualizes the non-critical audio dropout situation for the audience and Jamie Cullum on the London stage. Furthermore, we also took a closer look at the dropout situation in Birmingham at minute 200 of the total measurement duration. The results are illustrated in Figure 7. Here, we can see buffer underruns instead of buffer overruns in an interval of approximately 75 seconds. This measurement provides diagnosis of the reason for the measured dropouts: despite a common sample rate of 48 kHz, the unsynchronised distributed sound cards exhibit a slight clock drift. The frequency difference of significantly less than 1 Hz results in a faster (in Birmingham) and a slower (in London) sound card. Consequently – with respect to a reference time in-

Figure 5. Visual plot of the 200 minutes logged data received from Birmingham. The top shows the one-way latency (OWD), the middle shows the dropouts divided into under- and overruns, the bottom shows the amount of reordered packets.

interval – the faster card sends more audio buffers than the slower card and this leads to buffer overruns at the slower end and to buffer underruns at the faster end. Theoretically, each overrun corresponds to an underrun at the remote end. Practically, the jitter buffer on each site has an impact on the dropout interval: each time the sound card drift has exceeded the duration of an audio buffer, the faster end’s jitter buffer is decreased by one network packet until an underrun occurs. Then, the buffer is filled again and the process repeats periodically. On the slower end, however, the buffer overrun and the corresponding drop occur more often because the jitter buffer has no upper threshold: The already filled buffer cannot store more data and in turn the additional packet is dropped.

Additionally we observed around 65 UDP packets re-

Figure 6. Five-minute (300 seconds) time zoom illustration of audio dropouts at the London endpoint.

Figure 7. Five-minute (600 seconds) time zoom illustration of audio dropouts at the Birmingham endpoint.

ceived in the wrong order over the whole 200 minute event, as illustrated at the bottom of the graph. Due to the low probability, this purely network-related effect is negligible with respect to the audible impression in our performance. The actual sound of wrong ordered packets corresponds to error-concealed audio dropouts.

Figure 8. Visual plot of the 200 minutes logged data received from Bristol: The top shows the one-way latency (OWD), the middle shows the dropouts divided into under- and overruns, the bottom shows the amount of reordered packets.

Figure 8 shows the data received from the Bristol site. The one-way latency ranged between 17 and 27 ms also depending the actual buffer state. For this connection the jitter buffer size remained equal for every moment of our measurement. Audio dropouts occurred also for this link, however, with less significance and regularity. In contrast to Birmingham we can observe more buffer underruns than overruns. Furthermore, 28 wrong-ordered packets could be observed in total leading to the same effect as described for the Birmingham connection.

The measured results are in agreement with the local au-

dible impression on each of the stages: despite occasional audio dropouts, neither the artists nor the audience could hear any disruptions in the audio, providing a natural performing environment for the musicians. Regarding the measured latencies the results are in agreement with our previous cognitive findings for medium tempo pieces [1] as performed in this session: None of the musicians considered latency as problematic and everyone agreed that the character of this remote performance was equal to a situation with musicians performing in the same room. Media content including interviews with the musicians are available at the Music-For-All website [10] and give a better impression regarding the player’s feedback and the success of the whole event at the same time.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We successfully performed a distributed music session with music celebrity Jamie Cullum in London and numerous amateur musicians in Birmingham and Bristol. Sites were connected by a self-engineered and administrated 5G network, which lead to stable audio network delays of below approximately 25 ms by applying the Soundjack software. In this setup, it was possible to perform moderate tempo music pieces at a high level of precision and professionalism as recorded and documented in [10]. Via 5G we could basically achieve similar audio stream stability and latency compared with classical wired IP networks. Thanks to the stable 5G connection we could identify audio dropouts related to the sound card clock drift, which however were almost inaudible due to the application of error concealment policies. In the future, we plan to address this issue by applying a new concept of remote audio clock synchronisation. Overall, our event indicated the potential for 5G networks to open up a professional-quality distributed music experience to the general public as 5G networks are being rolled out. It will deliver on the promise of the Internet of Skills [9]; in our case, by enabling music teachers to deliver musical educational independent of location.

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